

Lactones of 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-1-(2-hydroxy-2-propyl)-2-naphthoic Acid

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The title compounds were prepared by acid-catalysed cyclisation of 6-phenyl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-2-methyl-3-oxohexane.

In connection with some synthetic experiments on aromatic cyclodehydration in our laboratory¹, we observed that the interaction between peri-substituents in the forming hydroaromatic rings exerts considerable influence on the yield and nature of the cyclised products. In the present communication, we wish to report an interesting example of this type. Cyclisation of ethyl α -phenethylacetoacetate with sulphuric acid to 3,4-dihydro-1-methyl-2-naphthoic acid is well-known² and proceeds with good yield. But a similar cyclisation of 6-phenyl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-2-methyl-3-oxo-hexane (I) did not go well with sulphuric acid and was effected with a mixture of sulphuric acid and phosphoric acid. Moreover, the product was not the expected dihydronaphthalene derivative (II) but a lactone (III), m.p. 106° which shows the following spectral properties: IR: ν_{\max} (nujol), 1752 cm⁻¹ (γ -lactone, rather low value), 1395 and 1380 cm⁻¹ (*gem*-dimethyl); NMR*: a broad singlet at 2.87 τ (4 H, aromatic), double centred at 6.4 τ (1H, benzylic, J = 10 cps), an irregular multiplet at 6.8 τ (1H, 3-methine), a triplet at 7.35 τ (2H, benzylic methylene), a multiplet at 7.95 τ (2H, methylene) and two sharp singlets (3H each) at 8.34 and 8.99 τ (two geminal methyl). The assignment of *cis* configuration is consistent with the mechanism of formation of the lactone from the unsaturated acid (II, with exocyclic double bond)³ by a concerted mechanism (attack of -CO₂H and H⁺ from opposite ends of the double bond) and is apparently supported by wide difference in chemical shift (0.65 ppm) of the two geminal dimethyl group. The corresponding difference in the *trans*-lactone (vide *infra*) is only 0.38 ppm; the model shows that in the *cis* configuration, one of the methyl group is nearer to the ring current of the phenyl and so is more shielded (8.99 τ).

The lactone (III) on alkaline hydrolysis afforded a hydroxy-acid (IV), m.p. 160° (acetate, m.p. 184°) which readily lost the elements of water giving the *trans* lactone (V), m.p. 132°; IR: 1778 cm⁻¹ (lactone), and 1402 and 1385 cm⁻¹ (geminal dimethyl); NMR: a broad singlet

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* NMR spectra were taken on a Varian 60 MC machine in deuterio-chloroform solution through the courtesy of Dr. D. N. Roy of Shade Tree Research Laboratory, Toronto University.

1. D. Nasipuri, R. Roy, and U. Rakshit, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **37**, 369; also R. Bhattacharya, D. Phil. (Science) Thesis, Calcutta University, 1968.
2. R. Roy, D. Phil. (Science), Thesis, Calcutta University, 1961.
3. C. K. Ingold, "Structure and Mechanism", Bell and Sons Ltd., 1953, p. 562.

at 2.83 τ (4H, aromatic), five closely spaced ($J = 4-5$ cps) peaks centred at 6.9 τ (3H, the two methine protons and one of the benzyl methylene protons), a broad range of multiplets at 7.1-8.1 τ (3H), and two sharp singlets (6H) at 8.20 and 8.58 τ . Apparently, epimerisation occurred during alkaline hydrolysis. Similarly, the lactone (VI), m.p. 160° was formed by the cyclisation of 6- α -naphthyl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-2-methyl-3-oxohexane.

(I)

(II)

(III)

(IV)

(V)

(VI)

The lactone (III) was converted into γ -chloroester by treatment with phosphorus pentachloride and ethanol, and the latter dehydrohalogenated to the unsaturated ester (as II). But dehydrogenation of the latter with sulphur followed by hydrolysis only afforded 2-naphthoic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

*Ethyl Isobutyrylacetate*⁴ (Ethyl *Ethyl 4-Methyl-3-oxopentanoate*): This was prepared by condensation of isobutyryl chloride with sodio-salt of ethyl acetoacetate and subsequent ammonolysis⁵ of the product.

Ethyl 6-Phenyl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-2-methyl-3-oxohexane (I): To a solution of sodium ethoxide prepared from sodium (5.75 g., 0.25 mole) and absolute ethanol (100 ml.), was added ethyl isobutyrylacetate (40 g., 0.25 mole). The mixture was cooled and phenethyl bromide (46 g., 0.25 mole) was dropped in. The mixture was refluxed for 15 hr. at 90° and the product worked up in the usual way. Ethyl 6-phenyl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-2-methyl-3-oxohexane (I) was obtained as a colourless oil (36 g., 55%), b.p. 150°/8 mm. (Found: C, 73.5; H, 8.7%; C₁₆H₂₂O₃ requires C, 73.3; H, 8.4%). It gave a deep violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

4. R. F. B. Cox, E. H. Kroeker and S. M. McElvin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 1172.

5. M. Guha and D. Nasipuri, *Organic Syntheses*, 1967, **42**, 41.

Lactones of 1,2,3,4-Tetrahydro-1-(2-hydroxy-2-propyl)-2-naphthoic Acid (III and V) :

(a) To a stirred mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid (20 ml.) and 89% phosphoric acid (10 ml.), the foregoing β -oxo-ester (I, 4 g.) was added at 0°. The mixture was stirred at this temperature for 20 hr. when a red colour developed. It was then decomposed with ice water. The organic matter was thoroughly extracted with ether, ethereal layer washed with water, dried (MgSO_4), and the solvent evaporated. The residue (3 g., 91%) solidified and was crystallised several times from petroleum (b.p. 68–80°) to furnish the lactone (III) in white needles, m.p. 106° (Found : C, 78.4; H, 7.7%; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.8; H, 7.4%).

(b) In another experiment, the β -oxo-ester (I, 4 g.) was cyclised with a mixture of sulphuric acid (45 ml.) and acetic acid (15 ml.) at 0° for 20 hr. The lactone (III) was obtained as a white crystalline solid (2.6 g., 79%).

Epimerisation of the Lactone (III) : The above lactone (0.5 g.) was refluxed with 10% ethanolic potassium hydroxide (1 g. in 10 ml. of ethanol) for 4 hr. The aqueous alkaline solution was cooled and carefully acidified with hydrochloric acid. A white amorphous solid was obtained, a part of which was crystallised from acetone and water without heating to afford the *hydroxy-acid* (IV) as colourless needles, m.p. 160° (Found : C, 71.6; H, 7.5%; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 71.8; H, 7.7%). The *acetate* was obtained by heating the acid (IV) with acetic anhydride and crystallised in white plates, m.p. 184° (Found : C, 70.2; H, 7.6%; $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 69.9; H, 7.3%). The rest of the hydroxy acid was converted to the *trans*-lactone (V) quantitatively by heating alone or with dilute mineral acid. It crystallised in long colourless needles (petroleum), m.p. 132° (Found : C, 78.2; H, 7.7%; $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 77.8; H, 7.4%).

Cyclisation of 6- α -Naphthyl-4-ethoxycarbonyl-2-methyl-3-oxohexane : Ethyl α -1-naphthyl-ethyl-isobutyrylacetate (1 g.) was added to a mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid (30 ml.) and water (10 ml.) and kept at 0° for 20 hr. The red product was decomposed with ice-water and filtered to afford the *lactone* (VI, 0.5 g.), m.p. 110–120°. On subsequent crystallisation, it was obtained in white clusters of needles, m.p. 158–160° (Found : C, 81.5; H, 6.5%; $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 81.2; H, 6.7%).

Attempted Dehydrogenation of the Lactone (III) : The lactone (III) (3.5 g.) was mixed with powdered phosphorus pentachloride (3.5 g.) and heated on the water bath for 1 hr. The mixture was cooled in ice and ethanol (2 ml.) was slowly dropped in and the whole kept overnight. Next day, the solution was poured over ice and the organic matter extracted with ether. The crude chloro-ester (5.2 g.), thus obtained was mixed with quinoline (20 ml.) and the mixture heated at 180–185° for 2 hr. The dark solution was cooled and poured into excess of dilute hydrochloric acid. The organic matter was taken in ethereal solution, dried, and solvent evaporated. The residual liquid on distillation yielded a colourless oil (1.8 g.), b.p. 140°/5 mm. which was analysed correctly for *ethyl 1-isopropylidihydro-2-naphthoic ester* (Found : C, 78.5; H, 8.0%; $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 78.6; H, 8.2%).

The ester (1.6 g.) was intimately mixed with powdered sulphur (0.22 g.) and heated at 240–250° for 2 hr. The crude material so obtained was hydrolysed with alkali and a semi-solid was obtained. This on being kept into contact with dilute methanol afforded

a crystalline solid (0.2 g.), m.p. 184°, found to be identical with a sample of 2-naphthoic acid.

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